

Component Parts of Linguistic Expertise

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 26 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 27 Nov 2024; **Published:** 28 Dec 2024

Abstract: Legal linguistics is a field of applied linguistics that has been developing rapidly in recent years. Linguistic expertise is the main area of this field. Linguistic expertise acts as a branch of forensic expertise, performs the function of explaining and commenting on various conflicting texts, clarifying abstractions. Of course, the task of linguistic expertise cannot be limited to this. The components of linguistic examination by world scientists are based in different ways from the point of view of legal and linguistics. The article sheds light on the components of linguistic expertise, specific aspects of the division of linguistic expertise into components in conflicting texts in the Uzbek language.

Keywords: Linguistic expertise, legal linguistics, object of linguistic expertise, conflicting texts, spoken and written speech identification, text authorization, general signs, private signs, voice messages, legal texts, official expertise, initiative expertise.

The process of examination of texts in different forms involves specific stages, and this process is completely different from linguistic analysis. Existing theoretical knowledge is put into practice and generalizations are made by the expert. Not every text can be the object of linguistic examination. Conflicting spoken and written texts can serve as a basis for linguistic expertise. Verbal texts, phone correspondence, audio and video messages, emergency calls can be public appeals aimed at various racial discrimination, insults, defamation, propaganda. The range of written texts is a bit wider. In particular, the linguistic examination of conflicting written texts can be divided into the following types:

- Miscellaneous personal correspondence;
- Anonymous letters;
- Newspaper materials;
- Messages published on Internet sites;
- Letters sent by e-mail;

In the linguistic examination of handwritten texts, the possibility of identifying various information such as the author's psychological state, age, and profession is quite high. In the criminological study of manuscript texts, general and specific signs of written speech are distinguished. General symptoms make it possible to determine and evaluate the lexical, grammatical, and stylistic capabilities of the author of the speech. Specific symptoms include non-literary elements, redundant words, incorrect use of phrases, repetition of words, lack of lexical vocabulary. This helps the expert to discover common aspects about the author.

There are different approaches on the part of specialists in dividing linguistic expertise into components. This field developed in the last decades of the twentieth century; In Magrachev's interpretation, linguistic

expertise is one of the branches of the legal field that deals with different types of research materials, substances, products, as well as materials science. However, another point of view is that, according to EIGalyashina and ERRossinskaya, linguistic expertise is a special type of expertise that belongs to the class of speech tests. According to the German scientist Jürgen Handkie, there are two important factors in linguistic expertise:

- Identification of voice messages;
- Identification of legal texts;

In the first round, the scientist emphasizes the need to pay attention to the phonetic features of the voice, the tempo and length of the voice, and in the identification of legal texts, he singles out suicide letters, questionnaire texts, and e-mail messages. According to IKBrinyev, it is not important to divide linguistic expertise into types in legal linguistics. The most important thing is the training of qualified specialists in the field. LVAzhnyuk indicates two main types of linguistic expertise that require special knowledge:

First, these are public texts published in the mass media or in any other direction (digital and print media, social networks, television and radio texts, programs, oral presentations, advertising texts, information for consumers of goods information and services, company names, etc.). In this case, language works as a tool of legal regulation.

Second, linguistic expertise in the regulation of social relations. In this case, various legal documents and personal correspondence serve as the main object. He proves his point by the following example: Clause X of the mortgage agreement gives reasons why the mortgage holder sends a specific formal request to the specified depositor (which has a certain legal effect). Clause Z of this mortgage agreement provides that the mortgage holder sends an official notice to the depositor, for other reasons, of a certain meaning (which has a different legal effect). The mortgage holder sends one official document (application-request) to the depositor, which means both an official notice and an official demand at the same time. The deposit questions the legality of such actions and comments on the legal ones.

The components identified by LVAzhnyuk are more general in comparison to the opinions given by other scientists and experts. The scientist relies on the main characteristics to distinguish between the two types and prefers to divide accordingly.

It can be said that the components of the linguistic experiment proposed by Anatoly Baranov are divided according to the form of organization:

- official expertise (performed at the request of the court and has a legal status);
- initiative expertise (performed at the request of any interested party (natural or legal entity)).

It seems that the author emphasizes the main parameters of linguistic expertise. Linguistic expertise is not always necessary. During the trial, based on the analysis of the testimony of the accused, the suspect, witnesses, and the available evidence, a verdict is issued according to the existing legal documents. However, there are situations that require not only existing legal documents, legal knowledge, but also special linguistic knowledge. In particular, accusations such as insult and defamation, damage to the position of an official; or to clarify the issue of authorization of anonymous letters and written texts in various forms (whether the author wrote it himself or not, whether there is external influence or not, phonetically, lexically and grammatically, which region's speech is characteristic of the representatives of the region? Etc.) in some cases, the knowledge and experience of a linguist-expert is needed. The first form of linguistic expertise distinguished by ANBaranov mentioned above is assigned in the same and similar situations.

Doctor of jurisprudence and philology, professor of Moscow State University named after OEKutafina, EIGalyashina, has conducted a number of studies on the issue of linguistic expertise, linguistic expertise of extremist materials, methods and methodology. In particular, in his research, he distinguishes the

following types of linguistic expertise:

- Linguistic expertise of title texts (by naming);
- Linguistic examination of normative-legal documents and acts;
- Linguistic examination of mass media texts and campaign materials, letters, addresses;
- Linguistic examination of works of science, literature and art;
- Linguistic examination of any speech material.

The components of the linguistic examination process were further refined. This line includes linguistic expertise of advertising texts; Linguistic examination of oral and written speech, unified trademarks and service marks; such as the linguistic examination of extremist materials.

In recent years, as a result of the development of science and socio-political relations, trademarks, as well as various new elements of naming, began to enter rapidly. Some of these names and signs do not affect the national appearance and characteristics of the people. As a result, there is a need for trademark linguistic expertise. In various linguistic literature, as well as in certain legal publications, the term trademark is used together with the term "trade name". At the same time, there is no clear division of the discussed concepts. In the current legislation, a trademark is defined as a sign that distinguishes the goods of certain legal entities or individuals from similar goods of other legal entities or individuals. A similar definition can be found in the linguistic literature.

According to TASoboleva and AVSuperanskaya: "A trademark is a special sign of commercial property that indicates who owns the exclusive right to dispose of the goods, to make a profit, and to cause damage for the delivery of a low-quality product." Trademarks perform functions similar to commercial names, namely, distinguishing, informative, nominative, catchy, etc. Therefore, trademarks also perform the function of information transport. Trademarks should perform security and guarantee functions.

Above we tried to think about the issue of components of linguistic expertise. It seems that each expressed opinion does not repeat each other, but at the same time, it corrects each other. These types of linguistic expertise are analyzed and based on world experience. However, Uzbek texts (oral and written) have national-ethnic characteristics, and the linguistic expertise of such texts acquires its own characteristics. In particular, texts in Uzbek literary language and texts in Uzbek dialects are not similar at all.

Differentiating them, it is natural that the methods and methods used in determining text authorization are also different. We believe that it is necessary to pay attention to these aspects of the issue when defining the types of linguistic expertise. To summarize our thoughts, it is appropriate to include the following components in the linguistic examination of Uzbek written texts:

- Linguistic examination of dialectological materials;
- Speech examination (gestures) expressed through non-verbal means of speech

Intensive interdisciplinary integration promotes collaboration and practical problem solving. From this point of view, linguistic knowledge works as an object of regulation in the legal field. Now the mutual cooperation of jurisprudence and linguistics serves the objective solution of the arising problems. Linguistic and legal knowledge are equally important in this process. Further improvement of the practical function of linguistics will lead to positive results not only in jurisprudence, but also in other branches of science. Now training of linguist-experts with high experience, knowledge and skills, development of the mechanism of improving their skills is one of the urgent issues of linguistic expertise.

After all, a linguist-expert has strict tasks and a responsible duty. A linguist-expert should be a specialist with deep linguistic, psychological and legal knowledge.

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